

FORMATION OF NATIONAL AND GENERAL CULTURAL BASIC COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7178472>

Abstract. This article describes the ways in which students form national and intercultural core competencies on a membership basis. The article also provides recommendations on the pedagogical process, the choice of teaching materials, aimed at the formation of national and intercultural core competencies in students. Today, the teacher's activity in the field of spiritual and moral education is of a very responsible nature and requires, first of all, the formation of an objective attitude towards mass culture among students. In this sense, the teacher must work in collaboration with the minds of art and culture in order to master innovations in this area, to be able to deeply analyze the situation in all its aspects.

Keywords: student, national and intercultural basic competence, membership, pedagogical process, teaching material, national values, moral relations, social environment, cultural worldview, art.

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНО-ОБЩЕКУЛЬТУРНЫХ БАЗОВЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. В этой статье описываются способы формирования у студентов национальных и межкультурных базовых компетенций. В статье также даны рекомендации по педагогическому процессу, выбору учебных материалов, направленных на формирование у студентов национальных и межкультурных профильных компетенций. Сегодня деятельность учителя в области духовно-нравственного воспитания носит очень ответственный характер и требует, прежде всего, формирования у учащихся объективного отношения к массовой культуре. В этом смысле учитель должен работать в сотрудничестве с умами искусства и культуры, чтобы овладеть нововведениями в этой области, уметь глубоко анализировать ситуацию во всех ее аспектах.

Ключевые слова: студент, национальная и межкультурная базовая компетенция, членство, педагогический процесс, учебный материал, национальные ценности, моральные отношения, социальная среда, культурное мировоззрение, искусство.

INTRODUCTION

The pedagogical process is presented, aimed at the formation of national and general cultural basic competencies, recommendations for the selection of educational materials. Today, the activity of a teacher in the field of spiritual and moral education is of a very responsible nature and, first of all, requires the formation of an objective attitude towards social culture among students. In this direction, the teacher must work in collaboration with artists and culture in order to master innovations in this area, be able to analyze the situation comprehensively.

The formation of a national educational ideal underlies the activities aimed at organizing the educational process. This is the main purpose of education. Highly moral ideas about a person as the main subject of national life determine the direction of education and development of students. The basis of the way of life of the Uzbek people is family relations, education and care of the state for its citizens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of the educational process is determined on the basis of the idea of forming a spiritually mature personality. One of the important tasks facing the state and society is the formation of a creative, enterprising personality with competence, high spirituality, who knows the history and culture of his people well, and implements it in his activities. The solution of such a problem requires a very complex pedagogical process, organized on the basis of modern requirements. The formation of a healthy spiritual and cultural worldview among students is influenced by the centuries-old experience of ancestors, the activities of teachers, spiritual and moral values, family traditions, the content of education, interpersonal social relations, the social environment, global information flows, the media, literature and art. That is why teachers working with students create the basis for the formation of a healthy spiritual and cultural worldview in them.

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 No. 187 "On approval of state educational standards for general secondary and secondary specialized, vocational education" defines the basic competencies necessary for the socialization of young people. These basic competencies are: communicative competence, information processing competence, self-development competence, socially active citizenship competence, national and general cultural competence, mathematical literacy, awareness and use of the achievements of science and technology, especially: self-development basic competence, national and general cultural basic competence requires, that both students and teachers have general cultural skills.

In the era of the information society, every schoolchild must learn from the first periods of his conscious life to independently search for the necessary information, to have a creative attitude to what he sees, reads and hears through the channels of art and culture, he must have the skills of critical analysis and evaluation of texts related to art and culture.

In the era of rapid development of information and communication technologies, the number of Internet users is increasing. In recent years, the Internet has become a global network. As a result, not only the information society has emerged in the world, but the processes of globalization in the world community have also accelerated. If we turn to the history of the information world, we will see that it went through a long evolutionary period until it reached its current level. The pedagogical skill of a modern teacher in everyday life is tested by difficult communication with teenagers who grow up in a highly informed and technocratic society. At present, the acquisition of national-cultural basic competence is one of the important qualities of a person, and its formation remains one of the urgent problems of general pedagogy. The art of mastering national and general cultural basic competencies in individual subjects is considered a synonym for cultural literacy.

RESULTS

In the Pedagogical Encyclopedia, it is interpreted as "Nationality is a set of features characteristic of a certain people, nation, distinguishing it from others." life. In order to know and understand nationalities, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the aspects that bring them together, along with the study of differences and differences between nations. Because the study of the achievements and positive experience of other nations, their assimilation enriches and develops the nation. The acquisition of basic national and cultural competencies requires each student to be creative in working with products of art and culture, information, communication

skills, critical thinking, identifying the main goals and hidden ideas transmitted by information, critical analysis and evaluation of art and culture. products, filtering information requires the formation and development of such skills.

Today, the activity of a teacher in spiritual and moral education is very responsible and, first of all, requires the formation of an objective point of view in students against mass culture. In this sense, the teacher must work in cooperation with the spirit of art and culture, master innovations in this area, and be able to comprehensively analyze emerging situations. It can be seen that the tasks assigned to the teacher are extremely complex. The teacher should be in a certain sense an actor, but in the process of improvisation carried out by the teacher, mistakes should not be made. Currently, rapid changes are taking place in various fields, such as art, culture, science and technology, and economics. Therefore, teaching students to accept new realities is an important task of the teacher. To do this, it is necessary to form students' knowledge about new realities and the competence to use them. According to the new requirements for education: to teach the student to acquire knowledge, to acquire new knowledge and skills and to form the ability to use them in life situations.

It is known that in order to ensure competitiveness in all spheres of life, each person must improve himself. Only then will such people move forward, achieve great success and rise spiritually. To do this, each person needs to regularly receive new knowledge. The role of the teacher in this place is incomparable. Because he must be able to creatively approach the educational process, while demonstrating his abilities. For this, it is important for a teacher to be able to create a mutually compatible environment in an educational institution. Education of students on the basis of high moral and ethical principles is a two-way pedagogical process. On the one hand, the teacher must mobilize all his abilities for the spiritual and moral development of students, the formation of their national and general cultural basic competencies, and on the other hand, as a specialist faithful to his profession, he must strive to acquire independent knowledge and encourage his students and colleagues to do the same. At the same time, the social environment that embodies students must be able to accept education as a phenomenon corresponding to it.

This means that it is important for the learning community to value education, and for a highly developed community to understand that it is a product of the learning process. The main task of the state and society in the field of education is for the teacher to be able to instill high moral standards through the heritage of our ancestors, to form in students an objective idea of "folk culture". National and general cultural basic competence forms students' artistic and cultural literacy, develops their speech, communication and creative thinking skills in the national, spiritual, aesthetic and intellectual terms.

DISCUSSION

In the modern information society, due to the fact that there are fewer opportunities to block and prohibit various kinds of information received from various pages, including YouTube, Mytube, Facebook, Telegram, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter, as well as to restrict the transmitted various stories, With the help of the Internet, the national and cultural formation of basic competencies among students will further increase the possibilities for its further development in the field of education. Of course, it is not for nothing that the need to form students' basic national-cultural and general cultural competencies in the process of the educational process is put on the agenda. In particular, according to the decree of the President of

the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on August 14, 2018, “On measures to educate young people with spiritual, moral and physical perfection, improve the quality of the education system to a new level”, the following is observed:

- Firstly, measures aimed at instilling loyalty to the Motherland and concern for its fate in the minds of the younger generation, the formation of their ideological immunity against the negative impact of alien ideas and views, are not effective enough;

- secondly, the activities of state bodies and public organizations in terms of strengthening loyalty to national and universal values, religious tolerance and interethnic harmony, as well as the formation of intolerance towards extremism, terrorism and other destructive ideas are not yet at the proper level;

- thirdly, the lack of cultural and entertainment institutions, out-of-school educational institutions, including various creative and educational circles, sports sections, necessary for the meaningful organization of free time for students and youth, negatively affects the healthy upbringing of children and the choice of the right lifestyle.

Attention is drawn to the presence in the educational material of certain features in the formation of national and general cultural basic competencies among students on the basis of integrity. In particular, when developing national and general cultural basic competencies in students, the educational material should encourage the student to creative work based on national traditions. An example of this would be a novel, short story, short story, film or series that does not prompt the reader to think, the same applies to light songs and music. They do not evoke high feelings in the student (a sense of patriotism, sympathy, kindness, generosity and honesty), but, on the contrary, awaken a tendency to a carefree lifestyle. National and universal values should be given priority in educational materials aimed at developing national and general cultural basic competencies in students. It should promote such virtues as patriotism, patriotism, modesty, correctness, diligence, intelligence, and, conversely, condemn laziness, betrayal of friends, parents, homeland, modesty, frivolity.

CONCLUSIONS

Educational materials aimed at the formation of national and general cultural basic competencies among students should be focused on the education of humanity, kindness, modesty, faith, conscience, neatness, purity, intelligence, patience, perseverance, kindness, adoration, words, generosity, gentleness; glorification of the figure of exemplary people, thinkers, their excellent qualities, brave and courageous people, people of high intelligence who fought for the freedom and development of the Motherland; It is necessary to reflect the thoughts of scientists about education, service to the country and people, excellent human characteristics and qualities.

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